

The Influence of Balanced Funds on the Development Budget in Kolaka Utara District, Southeast Sulawesi Province Period 2015-2019

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Abstract:- The Impact of the Development Budget Compensation Fund in the Administrative Area of North Kolaka, Southeast Sulawesi Province, 2015-2019. Thesis, Development Economics Study Program, Faculty of Economics, University of Muhammadiyah Makassar. Checked by Agus Salim HR and Asdar. The purpose of this research is to find out whether the compensation fund has an impact on the development budget. Quantitative methods based on secondary data obtained from the North Kolaka Central Bureau of Statistics (BPS) were used in this study. The data used is data analyzed by simple linear regression and processed in the SPSS 25 program. The results of the analysis of the distribution of assets in the development budget for the 2015-2019 Kolak Utara administration area show that the T-number is greater than the T-table, namely. H. T-number 4.099 > T-table 3.182 with a probability value of 0.012 less than 0.05 or 5%, namely H. Floating balance funds have a positive effect.

Keywords:- *Balanced Funds, Development Budget.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Balancing funds are regional funds originating from the APBN which consist of Revenue Sharing Funds (DBH), General Allocation Funds (DAU), and Special Allocation Funds (DAK). Balancing funds are intended not only to assist the regions in funding their authority, but also to reduce the imbalance in funding sources for the central and regional governments and to reduce the gap in government funding between regions. These three components of the balancing fund constitute a transfer system of funds from the government and constitute one unified whole.

III. DISCUSSION

Table 1: Realization of Regional Apparatus Expenditure Budget in North Kolaka Regency

Year	Fiscal	Realization	Percentage (%)
2015	808 061 509,08	754 081 027,98	20,11
2016	907.021.272,68	872.676.620,24	15,72
2017	799.677.225,55	745.708.553,59	-14,54
2018	855.251.845,94	779.038.128,16	4,46
2019	889.101.785,00	878.766.610,67	12,80

Source: Data from the Central Bureau of Statistics for North Kolaka Regency, 2021.

The financial balance between the government and the regional government includes the distribution of finance between the government and the regional government in a proportional, democratic, fair and transparent manner by taking into account the potential, conditions and needs of the region. The financial balance between the government and regional government is an integral part of the regulation of the state financial system, and is intended to regulate the funding system for government authority that is delegated, delegated, and assigned to the regions.

II. METHODS

The type of research used in this research is quantitative research. Quantitative research is a systematic scientific study of the parts and phenomena as well as the causality of their relationships.

According to Sugiyono, this type of quantitative research is a research method based on positive philosophy. This method is used in examining the sample and research population, the sampling technique is generally done by random or random sampling.

Table 2: Realization of the Capital Expenditure Budget (Development Budget) in North Kolaka Regency

Year	Fiscal	Realization	Percentage (%)
2015	733 187 621,72	749 382 697,28	19,19
2016	829 358 764,24	817 539 815,86	9,09
2017	780 535 051,85	761 873 952,17	-6,80
2018	823 873 759,94	824 185 304,89	8,17
2019	877.292.410,00	877.292.419,00	6,44

Source: Data from the Central Bureau of Statistics for North Kolaka Regency, 2021

Based on the results of the analysis that has been carried out with a number of stages of previous examination regarding data and methods, it can be explained the relationship between balancing funds and the development budget in North Kolaka Regency.

Balancing funds have a positive and significant effect on the development budget in North Kolaka Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This is evidenced from the results of data processing where the variable coefficient value is 0.625 with a t-count value of 4.099 greater than t-table 3.182 ($4.099 > 3.182$). And it is also proven from a significant value of 0.026 ($0.026 < 0.05$).

This happens because changes in the development budget have a relationship with fluctuations in the receipt of balancing funds, meaning that quantitatively it can be said that every time there is a change in the allocation of the balancing fund budget in a certain year, it will also be followed by changes in the development budget.

So it can be concluded that the balancing fund (X) has a positive and significant effect on the development budget (Y) in North Kolaka Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. The results of this study are in line with research conducted by Sulastri Dewi (2019) and Sudi Surahman (2019), where it was found that balancing funds had a positive and significant effect on the development budget.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion described in the previous chapter, it can be concluded that balancing funds have a positive and significant effect on the development budget in North Kolaka Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province. This is evidenced from the results of data processing where the variable coefficient value is 0.625 with a t-count value of 4.099 greater than t-table 3.182 ($4.099 > 3.182$) and also proven from a significant value of 0.026 ($0.026 < 0.05$). This happens because changes in the development budget have a relationship with fluctuations in the receipt of balancing funds, meaning that quantitatively it can be said that every time there is a change in the allocation of the balancing funds budget in a certain year, it will also be followed by changes in the development budget.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Arsyad, Lincoln. 2010. Introduction to Regional Economic Planning and Development. (BPFE Yogyakarta).
- [2.] Chalit, R.A. 2011. Regional Revenue & Budget Management. Publisher Graha Ilmu: Yogyakarta.
- [3.] Ateng, Syafruddin. Government Coordination Arrangements in the Regions. Publisher: Tarsito, 1976.
- [4.] Ardhani, Pungky. 2011. Effects of Economic Growth, and Special Allocation Funds on Capital Expenditure Budget Allocation (Study on District/City Governments in Central Java). Thesis. (published). Semarang : Diponegoro University
- [5.] Aramana D. (2011). The effect of regional original income, balancing funds and other legitimate regional income on regional spending with local government financial performance as a moderating variable in the province of North Sumatra.
- [6.] Didi Nuryadin, Sri Suharsih (2017). Analysis and evaluation of the impact of special allocation funds on development performance indicators in the district-city case study areas in 2003-2013.
- [7.] Hoed, Benny Hoedoro,. 1998. Development Planning. BAPPENAS KORPRI Unit, Jakarta, p. 67-72.
- [8.] Huang, Hidayat. 2021. Simple Regression Analysis, Here's the Explanation. Ministry of National Development Planning/Bappenas, Principals of the 2000 development budget.
- [9.] La Mente. 2009. Contribution of Local Revenue to Regional Revenue and Expenditure Budget in Supporting the Implementation of Regional Autonomy in Makassar City. Makassar City, South Sulawesi
- [10.] Monev, 2020. Definition of Development and Multidimensionality.
- [11.] Muh. Zainul Arifin (2018). Management of the village development budget in Bungin Tinggi village, Sirah subdistrict, Pulau Padang, Ogan Komering Ilir district, South Sumatra province.
- [12.] Home Affairs Minister No. 32 Years (2008), Implementation of Decentralization.
- [13.] Rahman. Fatur (2013). Analysis of local government financial performance and its influence on regional spending and PAD in Jambi Province, University of Jambi.

- [14.] Republic of Indonesia. 2000. Government Regulation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 104 of 2000 concerning Balancing Funds.
- [15.] Riva Ubar Harahap (2011). The Influence of General Allocation Funds, Special Allocation Funds, and Revenue Sharing Funds on the Human Development Index in Districts/Cities of North Sumatra Province. Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra.
- [16.] Sugiyono. 2008. Qualitative Quantitative Research Methods and R&D, Bandung: ALFABETA
- [17.] Sudi Surahman (2019). The influence of the development budget on economic growth in East Luwu district for the 2014-2018 period, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar.
- [18.] Sukino, Sadono, 2015. "Introductory Macroeconomic Theory". Jakarta: Rajawali Press, 2015
- [19.] Sri Sulastris Dewi (2019). The effect of balancing funds on regional capital expenditure in Takalar district, South Sulawesi Province, Muhammadiyah University of Makassar.
- [20.] Todaro, Michael P., 1998. Economic Development in the Third World. Jakarta: Erlangga. Todaro, Michael P. and Stephen C. Smith, 2006, Economic Development In The World Third, Eighth Edition, Erlangga, Jakarta.
- [21.] Tangkumahat, Vicky V. J. Panelewen, Arie D. P. Mirah (2017). Village fund program to increase development and economy in Pineleng District, Minahasa Regency
- [22.] Walidi. 2009. The Effect of General Allocation Funds on Per Capita Income, Capital Expenditures as Intervening (Case Study in North Sumatra Province). Master's thesis for USU's Postgraduate Program. Medan.
- [23.] Huang, Hidayat. 2011. Simple Linear Regression Analysis. Here's the Explanation. <https://www.globalstatistik.com/analysis-regressi-impact-this-explanation>.